
STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF BUSINESS STUDIES IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, ENUGU STATE.

OKONKWO CHUKWUDI JOSEPH

Department of Cooperative Economics and Management.

Our Saviours' Institute of Science, Agriculture and Technology, Enugu. (OSISATECH)

E-mail: jochy2kng@yahoo.com

UGWA MAGNUS

Department Of Business Administration and Management

Our Saviours' Institute of Science, Agriculture and Technology, Enugu. (OSISATECH)

E-mail: magnusugwa@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Business Studies, as a discipline, is a relatively new comer into the Nigerian educational system. It marked its entrance into the Nigerian Educational system in 1981, when the National Policy on Education through its enactment made it compulsory that business studies is taught in all secondary schools in Nigeria. This study discussed the strategies for effective teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools. Seven (7) research questions were raised and twenty (20) items of questionnaire was extracted from the seven (7) research questions. Related literatures were reviewed. The research design is survey research; the area of the study is Enugu-North Local Government Area of Enugu State. The population of the study is 702 teachers, and 14,046 students. The simple random sampling technique was used to select two hundred (200) respondents from eight (8) secondary schools in Enugu-North Local Government Area. The instrument used for data collection is questionnaire. However, the data collected were organized using frequency table. Mean scores from a five (5) point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U,) Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) was used. The cut off point was 3.50; hence any mean score below 3.50 was rejected while any mean score equal to or above 3.50 was accepted. The result obtained showed that factors affecting the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies includes availability of resources, the attitude of students, the role of teachers, government, non-governmental organizations and stakeholders. It was observed that where ever these factors were lacking teaching and learning was affected negatively. It was recommended that adequate funding of public schools, provision of teaching and learning facilities, training of teachers and staff, adequate incentives for teachers and students alike should be provided.

Key words: Business studies, strategies, teaching and learning.

Introduction

Teaching and learning can be described as inseparable as far as human development is concerned. Teaching is teacher-centered while learning is people, pupil or student oriented. Ifeagwu (2000) defined teaching as a two-way traffic system involving exchange of ideas between the teacher and the students. He further defined teaching as a series of activities geared towards helping students “learn how to learn”. While learning can be defined as the behavioural change that takes place at the end of a teacher-student interaction in a classroom setting. In order words, learning is the experience gained from interactions. According to Burns (1995:p95) learning is conceived as a relatively

permanent change in behavior with behavior including both observable activity and internal process such as thinking, attitude and emotions.

Business studies is a subject that requires a high level of synchrony between teacher and learner, to make an impact. Business studies is an integrated subject and is made up of five component subjects – Shorthand, Typewriting, Book-keeping, Commerce and office Practices (Anioke, 2005). According to the National Policy on Education (1981), (1998) and (2002) business studies which comprises of shorthand, typewriting, commerce, office practice and book keeping is a compulsory subject at the Junior Secondary School level of Education.

Component subjects of business studies are charged with impacting different skill to the learner. Shorthand as a subject is a method of rapid writing by means of abbreviations and symbols, used especially for taking dictation. Typewriting on the other hand is simply writing down with a typewriter. The subject typewriting teaches the skill of writing with a typewriters. Also, Book-keeping as a subject involves learning the skill of keeping records of all financial transactions in a business. The subject commerce concerns itself with the activity of buying and selling, especially on a large scale. Lastly, office practice is concerned with familiarizing the students with and about the concepts of theory and practices of business organizations, office machines, their meanings and importance.

Business studies, while offered in junior secondary school, it is taken from class One (J.S.S 1) through class three (J.S.S. 3). While in senior secondary school, students offer accounts, commerce, economics, shorthand, and typewriting as separate subjects despite the fact that subjects like typewriting and shorthand are gradually being replaced with the computer.

Statement of the Problem

The subject Business Studies has in recent times struggled to survive as a subject in secondary schools in Enugu north local government area of Enugu State. The subject has experienced limited number of students offering to study it as well as a total removal of the subject from some schools' curriculum due to lack of students. Paul (2005) identified one of the problems encountered in the study of business studies as lack of suitable equipment and supplies for the teaching of business study.

Secondly, there is the problem of apathy on the part of some school administrators and their staff which results in their deliberately ignoring business studies as a programme or relegating the programme totally. Also apathy on the part of the non-business students towards business students, which results in either superiority or inferiority complex.

Again, there is a problem of discontinuity of students who studied business studies in secondary school from pursuing a high studies in the university, polytechnic and college of education or even practicing skills acquired from the study. This disconnection is one of the reasons this research study is being embarked on.

Finally, there is the problem of skilled and well qualified personnel to teach the business related courses. This is a major reason why studying of business studies is some worth uncomfortable and uninteresting for students offering the subject.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of this study is to find out the strategies for effective teaching and learning of business studies in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

The specific purposes of this study are to;

1. Find out contribution of teachers to the effectiveness of teaching and learning of Business Studies.
2. Find out student's role in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools.
3. Find out the role of resource/facilities in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies.
4. Find out the duties of the educational administration and management in teaching and learning of Business Studies.
5. Find out the role of government and non-governmental organization in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Research Questions

1. What are the contributions of teachers to the effectiveness of teaching and learning of Business Studies?
2. What are the roles of students in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools?
3. What are the roles of resources/facilities in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies?
4. What are the duties of the educational administration and management in teaching and learning of Business Studies?
5. What are the roles of government and non-governmental organization in improving teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is restricted to teaching and learning of Business Studies in Enugu State, which is based on the students in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of the state. The scope is centered on the strategies for effective teaching and learning of Business Studies, the role of teachers and that of students to the course, the duties of educational administration and management, the expectation from government and non-governmental organization in seeing to its effectiveness.

Significance of the Study

This research work is important in developing the entrepreneurial skill in the students at an early age. When teaching and learning becomes more effective, the youngster are more independent minded in their approach to life rather than dependent on the government for employment. This study would improve and increase the productivity of the teachers as well as educational institutions. Studies like this, highlights areas where teaching is deficient as well as administrative flaws.

This study is important, in that it will assist policy makers as well as governments to enact laws and establish policies in line with positive research recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

The origin of the earliest form of business education can be traced to apprenticeship training. According to Osuala (2004), Popham, Schrag, and Blocklvs (1971) and Njoku (2006), business education started from apprenticeship training. Most places of apprenticeship were privately owned. The proprietary business gained prominence in the middle of the 19th century, and until the early 20th century it was the primary producer of trained workers for businesses (Nwokocha, 2005). The period of training and impacting of skills varied from one trade to another. Payment for training was either in cash or in form of a mortgage of land or any valuable property.

As time went on business started growing, Popham (1975) recorded that more people were needed in businesses therefore, the idea of restricting training to certain places was not achieving much so itinerant tutors started traveling around the country (USA) giving instructions in book keeping and penmanship. People started appreciating the need for business skills, schools started including book-keeping, penmanship and commercial arithmetic in the curricula as a result of demand for commercial training. This gave business education a place in the formal setting.

The period between 1959-1976 marked the era in which most states in Northern Nigeria established commercial schools or opened up commercial departments in existing secondary schools to offer commercial subjects. Prior to this period, while the existing commercial centres in the North were privately operated, the other Southern states had this programmes running in government recognized established schools. By 1960, schools in Lagos, Ibadan, Enugu, Kaduna and Auchi were established. These colleges trained senior and middle level technical personnel. They offered two and three years courses in commerce, accountancy, secretarial studies and other fields, leading to the intermediate examinations and particularly city and guilds institute of London and Royal society of Art (RSA) (Nwokocha, 2005).

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 1977) in its candid nature deplored the attitude with which the public regards technical/commercial education. This policy portrayed the Federal Government interest and preparedness to develop vocational education programmes. The major aim of vocational education programmes is to provide trained man-power for Nigeria technology and commerce. This in effect will boost the country's industrial, commercial and economic development. Realizing the importance and need of education and technical education, the 1977 policy on education was revised. In 1981, the revised national policy on education laid much emphasis on the fundamental necessity of vocational education, by making (as a point of policy) all the secondary schools to start these commercial courses right from the beginning of the first year in secondary school.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.

This research is based on the Classical behavioural (Stimulus-response) theory of Edward Thorndike.

Edward L. Thorndike (1874-1949) is well known for his laws of learning. One of his major laws of learning includes the law of effect. This law states that an act which results in an animal's experiencing satisfaction in a given situation will generally become associated with that situation so that when it recurs that act will also be likely to recur. The idea is that pleasure and pain as consequences of our acts are important determination of behaviour. We all do those things that give us pleasure and naturally avoid those things that give us pain.

The Law of effect arose as a result of an experiment which he carried out using a hungry cat locked up in a cage with a tempting morsel of fish outside. The only way to unlock the cage was by pulling

a string hanging inside the cage. The cat was able to discover this after several attempts of making frantic efforts to find its way out. Its effort was rewarded by the door opening and its being able to get at the fish. The test was repeated several times and it was discovered that it took the cat shorter and shorter time to open the door of the cage and reach the fish outside. After several studies, Thorndike concluded that it was not by the cat's reasoning nor by his instinct that he learnt to pull the string rather it was due to the gradual stamping in of the stimulus response connection between seeing the string and pulling it. That is to say, if a stimulus was followed by a response and then by a satisfier, the stimulus-response connection would be strengthened. If however, a stimulus was followed by a response and then by an annoyer, the stimulus-response connection would be weakened. Thus, satisfying and annoying effects of responses determined whether the stimulus-response connections would be stamped in or stamped out.

The Law of effect was later modified to read the Law of exercise. This simply means that satisfying consequences serve to re-inforce stimulus response bonds. It was further modified to read the law of readiness. This law states that a learner's satisfaction is determined by the extent of his "preparatory set" that is readiness for action. Thorndike's theories are of great importance to the teacher. The emphasis on the S-R bond reminds teachers of the importance of viewing all his activities as contributions to the learning process; lesson planning, instruction and evaluation of learning.

Contribution to the Teaching of Business Studies

Thorndike's theories have contributed immensely to the teaching of Business Education (Business Studies) in the following ways.

Practice: Business studies which consist of shorthand, typewriting, bookkeeping, commerce and office practice is geared towards skill acquisition. The skills can only be acquired through practice. In the Thorndike's experiment, the cat was able to perform less random activity with subsequent trials until it operates the release mechanism once it finds itself in the cage. According to Isiaka and Dagosta (2001), this is analogous to the theory of vocational education which states that training should help the trainee to capitalize his interest and abilities to the highest possible degree. In other words, incorrect experiences will diminish and the correct ones get fixed with constant practice. Business studies is rooted in acquisition of skills and as such learning cannot be effective by watching someone else perform the action.

Motivation: Thorndike's theories contain element of motivation. Motivation is a learning process which is constantly applied in business education instruction. This is a way by which an individual is energized so as to learn better.

Need for Students to Work at Their Own Pace: Another useful outcome of the stimulus response theories is the need for students to work at their own pace. This means that your students' stages of development, maturation and environmental differences should be taken into consideration when teaching.

Need to Learn the Specific Behaviours That are Necessary Through Discrimination:

Thorndike's learning theories emphasize the necessity to discriminate between different behaviours. Thorndike's cat was able to discriminate between different structures in the cage and capitalized on the release mechanism whenever it wants to obtain food. Therefore when teaching, ensure that you emphasize the need for your students to learn specific behaviours that are needed for efficient job performance.

Reinforcement: Reinforcement is one of the key principles of learning. Food reinforces response, it is the reward for a particular action taken by the cat therefore it repeats it again and again. This also applies to learning business studies. Reinforcement is a way to encourage what has been learnt in order to make it part of the individual and this is achieved through constant practice. Praise always follows a job well done and deep appreciation for efficient mastery of skills has always been part of teaching/learning process for business studies.

EMPIRICAL STUDY

THE MEANING OF BUSINESS STUDIES

According to Parkhill (2011) Business Studies is a dynamic course which prepares students for the challenges of 21st century by introducing them, to the world of business. It emphasizes the ever changing character of business, the diverse nature of business enterprise and the inter-dependence of the various parts of the business world. As an academic subject business studies is practical, applied and exciting. It equips students with many life skills such as communication skill, problem solving skill, time management skills, teamwork and decision-making skills whether your aim is to pursue an academic career, train for a profession or become an entrepreneur the necessary knowledge and skills will be provided.

According to the Federal Government in its National Policy on Education (1981), (1998) and (2002). Business Studies which comprises of shorthand, typewriting, commerce, office practice and book-keeping is compulsory subject at junior secondary school level of education.

The National Policy on Education (NPE) further provides that on completion of the junior secondary school, students should be streamed into senior secondary school, the technical college, vocational training centre and the apprenticeship scheme on the basis of 60%, 20%, 10% and 10% respectively.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVE OF STUDYING BUSINESS STUDIES

According to McShare (2011), teaching and learning of business studies in Nigeria secondary schools has the under listed aims and objectives. They include;

1. To maintain and/or stimulate student's curiosity, interest and enjoyment in business studies.
2. To enable students to be familiar with a body of business and economics knowledge, principles, skills and vocabulary.
3. Also, to enable students to see business studies in the context of a wider body of knowledge and skill.
4. To help students to develop a range of skills like politeness, perseverance, initiative and ability to work independently as well as part of a team.
5. To employ teaching methods and resources that allows all students to have equal access to business studies and to experience success and enjoyment in their business studies work.
6. To develop an awareness in students of the implications of business and industry (past and present) for the individual, the community and the environment.

Research Methodology

The design for this study is the survey. This design was chosen because the study solicited the perceptions of the respondents. For this research work, 20 (twenty) items in a 5 point scale

questionnaire were administered. . The response format is: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD).

The population consists of all the teachers and students of all the secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. According to the Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB) statistical unit of Enugu educational zone of 2012/2013 study year or academic session, the population of teachers was 702, while that of students was 14, 046.

The researcher selected 8(eight) secondary schools from all the secondary schools within the area of study. However, 25 respondents were randomly picked from each of the selected secondary schools giving a total of two hundred (200) respondents. Two hundred and forty (240) copies of questionnaire was distributed to secondary school students, teachers and staff in eight (8) secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area. Two hundred and twenty-two were returned, from which two hundred (200) were randomly picked; which formed the copies used.

DECISION RULE

An item is accepted when the mean is equal to or greater than 3.50, but rejected if below 3.50 cut off point.

Results

The data collected in the process of this study were organized using the frequency distribution tables.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

The contribution of teachers to teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area.

Table 1 Contributions of teachers

		SA	A	D	SD	U	TOTAL	MEAN	
S/N	ITEMS	5	4	3	2	1	(T)	(X)	DECISION
1.	Business studies teachers are dedicated and industrious in their teaching in Enugu North Local Government Area.	132	56	4	4	4	200	4.54	Accepted
		660	224	12	8	4	908		
		75	85	27	7	6	200	4.08	Accepted
		375	340	81	14	6	816		
	GRAND MEAN							4.31	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 1, items 1 and 2 recorded mean scores of 4.54 and 4.08 respectively, with the grand mean of 4.31. From the above record, all items recorded mean scores that are above the cut-off point of 3.50, therefore they are all accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

How does boosting the interest of the students play roles in the effective teaching and learning of business studies?

Table 2 Student’s role in improving teaching and learning

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
3.	Organizing business studies competitions with attractive prizes for students of secondary schools in Enugu North will enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies	133	46	8	8	5	200	4.47	Accepted
		665	184	24	16	5	894		
4.	Proper guidance and counseling services in secondary school will enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies	65	61	15	41	18	200	3.57	Accepted
		325	244	45	82	18	714		
5.	Encouragement of the students by their parents like buying of Business Studies text books, educational CDs on Business Studies for them, sponsoring them on extra training/lesson etc can enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies	129	42	20	3	6	200	4.43	Accepted
		645	168	60	6	6	885		
GRAND MEAN								4.16	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 2, items 3-5 recorded mean scores of 4.47, 3.57 and 4.43 respectively, with the grand mean of 4.16. From the above record, all items recorded mean scores that are above the cut off point of 3.50, therefore they are all accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

How does the availability of resources/facilities help in the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies in Enugu North Local Government Area?

Table 3 Effect of availability of resources/facilities

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
6.	Provision of teaching and learning facilities like information communication Technology(ICT), internet facilities and Instructional	131	47	6	16	0	200	4.47	Accepted

	materials will enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies	655	188	18	32	0	893		
7.	Provision of well stocked libraries in secondary schools will enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies.	80	42	39	31	8	200	3.78	Accepted
		400	168	117	62	8	755		
8.	Proper funding of schools so that instructional materials etc can adequately be provided in schools will enhance teaching and learning.	71	56	30	41	2	200	3.77	Accepted
		355	224	90	82	2	753		
	GRAND MEAN							4.0	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 3, items 6-8 recorded mean scores of 4.47, 3.78 and 3.77 respectively, with the grand mean of 4.0. From the above record, all items are above the cut off point of 3.50, therefore they are all accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 4

What are the duties of educational administration and management in the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies in Enugu North Local Government Area?

Table 4 Duties of educational administration and management

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
9.	Effective supervision of teachers and inspection of secondary schools will enhance effective teaching and learning of Business Studies.	120	25	37	18	0	200	4.24	Accepted
		600	100	111	36	0	847		
10.	Organizing seminars, symposia, lectures etc to enlighten and sensitize Business Studies teachers, students and school authorities in the importance of Business Studies will enhance teaching and learning.	123	51	14	9	3	200	4.41	Accepted
		615	204	42	18	3	882		
	GRAND MEAN							4.32	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 4, items 9 and 10 recorded mean scores of 4.24 and 4.41 respectively, while the grand mean is 4.32. From the above record, all items recorded mean scores that are above the cut off

point of 3.50, therefore they are all accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 5

How does the role of Government, non-governmental organization and other stakeholders enhance the effective teaching and learning of Business studies in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Table 5 Role of Government, non-governmental organization and other stakeholders

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
11.	Organizing in-service and on the job training for Business studies teachers will improve the quality of teachers in teaching Business studies.	121	74	3	0	2	200	4.56	Accepted
		605	296	9	0	2	912		
12.	Provision of teaching and learning facilities like the state of the art facilities will improve effective teaching and learning of Business Studies.	133	47	20	0	0	200	4.57	Accepted
		665	188	60	0	0	913		
13.	Promotion and rewarding of dedicated and industrious teachers and staff will enhance effective teaching and learning.	134	41	16	8	1	200		Accepted
		670	164	48	16	1	899	4.5	
14.	Improving the salaries and welfare package for the teachers and staff will improve the teaching and learning of Business Studies	140	47	9	4	0	200	4.62	
		700	188	27	8	0	923		
	GRAND MEAN							4.56	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 5, items 11-14 recorded mean scores of 4.56, 4.57, 4.5 and 4.62 respectively with the grand mean of 4.56. From the above record, all items recorded mean scores that are above the cut off point 3.50, therefore they are all accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 6

How does the quality, quantity and attitude of teachers enhance the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies?

Table 6 Effect of quality, quantity and attitude of teachers

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
15.	The number of Teachers, paying teachers well and improving their welfare to boost their morale will enhance effective teaching and learning Business Studies in Enugu North Local Government Area.	138	53	6	3	0	200	4.63	Accepted
		690	212	18	6	0	926		
	GRAND MEAN							4.63	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 6, item 15 recorded a mean score of 4.63 and a grand mean score of 4.63, which is above the cut-off point of 3.50. Therefore, it is accepted.

RESEARCH QUESTION 7

What is the condition of teaching and learning Business studies in secondary schools in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State?

Table 7 Conditions of teaching and learning

S/N	ITEMS	SA 5	A 4	D 3	SD 2	U 1	TOTAL (T)	MEAN (X)	DECISION
16.	Enough time/periods are allocated for Business Studies lessons.	57 285	81 324	51 153	11 22	0 0	200 784	3.92	Accepted
17.	Business Studies lesson are conducive for learning.	60 300	116 464	18 54	5 10	1 1	200 829	4.15	Accepted
18.	Students are highly interested in the subject Business Studies	100 500	44 176	51 153	3 6	2 2	200 837	4.19	Accepted
19.	Teachers give adequate Continuous Assessment Tests and assignments regularly to the students.	111 555	72 288	11 33	5 10	1 1	200 887	4.4	Accepted
20.	There are enough facilities, instructional materials for teaching and learning Business Studies.	15 75	45 180	44 132	96 192	0 0	200 579	2.89	Rejected
	GRAND MEAN							3.92	Accepted

Source: Field survey 2015.

In table 7, items 16-20 recorded mean scores of 3.92, 4.15, 4.19, 4.4 and 2.89 respectively, with the grand mean of 3.92. From the above record, all the items apart from item 20 are above the cutoff point of 3.50, therefore they are all accepted but item 20 is rejected.

Findings

1. It was discovered that varying methods of teaching of Business Studies has helped in the effectiveness of teaching and learning of the subject.
2. It was discovered that availability of resources/facilities matters a lot for effective teaching and learning of Business Studies. However, facilities, instructional materials etc are not enough.
3. It was discovered that if teacher's attitude and interest are boosted by organizing seminar, symposia, lectures, for them in business studies, paying them well, increasing their number in schools by employing more teachers who are Business Studies experts and properly supervising them will enhance the effective teaching and learning of business studies.
4. It was also discovered that provision of all teaching and learning facilities, resources, quality teachers etc can boost the morale of students and motivate them to learn more.

5. Lastly, it was discovered that government has not helped as expected in enhancing the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies. Proper funding of schools, training and re-training of teachers, improving of infrastructures, provision of teaching and learning facilities, among other things have been neglected by the government.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the findings of the study, it was discovered that varying methods of teaching of Business Studies has helped in the effectiveness of teaching and learning of the subject.

Also, the availability of resources/facilities matters a lot for effective teaching and learning of Business Studies in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State. However, it was discovered that there are no enough facilities, instructional materials etc for teaching and learning of Business Studies within the area of study.

The study also discovered that if teacher's attitude and interest are boosted by organizing seminar, symposia, lectures, for them in business studies, paying them well, increasing their number in schools by employing more teachers who are Business Studies experts and properly supervising them will enhance the effective teaching and learning of business studies in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Furthermore, the study's discovered just as Owolabi and Jegede (2005) opined, that provision of all teaching and learning facilities, resources, quality teachers etc can boost the morale of students and motivate them to learn more.

Lastly, it was discovered that government has not helped as expected in enhancing the effective teaching and learning of Business Studies in secondary schools especially in Enugu North Local Government Area. Proper funding of schools, training and re-training of teachers, improving of infrastructures, provision of teaching and learning facilities, among other things have been neglected by the government. This agrees with Bada, Adewole and Olaleka (2006) who lamented that the government has performed below achieving the objectives of the National Policy on Business Studies Education.

Conclusion

Teaching and learning of business studies in secondary schools especially in Enugu North Local Government Area of Enugu State has come to stay. Therefore, teachers, students, parents, governments and other stakeholders should play their roles very well in other to uphold the objectives of National Policy on Education Business Studies. This will in no small measure increase the dignity of our educational system not only in Enugu North Local Government Area but also in our state and nation at large.

Recommendations

1. There should be training and re-training of teachers and staff and upward review of their salaries. Schools should be properly funded and provision of the needed facilities ensured.
2. Also, hardworking students and teachers of business studies should be adequately rewarded to encourage them to put in their best.

3. Finally, quiz competitions on business studies should be organized from time-to-time in secondary schools especially in Enugu North Local Government Area, in other to create awareness on the importance of business studies Education.

REFERENCE

- Anioke, B.O. (2005). *Modern Methods of Teaching Business Courses*. Modern Printers and Publisher, Emene Enugu.
- Alaezi, I. (1990). *The Nigerian New School Curriculum: Issues & Insight*, Jos. Ehindero (Nig) Ltd.
- Bade, T; Adewole A.;and Olaleka, O. (2006). *Uses of Computer and Its Relevance To Teaching And Learning*.
- Burns, R. (1995). *The Adult Learner at Work*. Sydney: Business & Professional Publishing.
- Daugherty, A. S. (1974). *Methods of Basic Business and Economic Education*. Cincinnati Ohio: South-Western Publishing Co.
- Gana, F. Z. (1987). *Business Education in Nigeria*. Past, Present and Future, BUSINESS EDUCATION JOURNAL II (1), 4-7.
- Harms, H.; Stehr, B. W. & Harris, E. E. (1972). *Methods of Teaching Business and Distributive Education*. Cincinnati, Ohio: South- Western Publishing Co.
- Ifeagwu, D. (2000). *Special Methods Teaching Practice for Students and Teachers in Africa*. Lagos: DIC Publishing Company.
- Igbinoba et al (2008), EDU 282 Business Education Methods: Course Guide. National Open University of Nigeria. Lecture Module
- Isiaka, B. T. and Dagosta, F. A. (2001). *Vocational and Technical Education Methods*. Lagos: Alografiks Kommunikations Company.
- Nigeria Education System. Educational Research and Review 4(10) 444.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1980), (1981) (1998), (2002), *Nigerian Policy on Education* Lagos:NERDC Press.
- McShane, L. (2011) Objectives of Business Studies. www.eduresource.com
- Nathaniel, O. J. (2010) *Child Psychology*. Unpublished lecture note. OSISATECH College Of Education, Enugu.
- Nwankwo I.O. (2009) *Educational Technology for Nigeria Schools*. Unpublished lecture note. Institute of Ecumenical Education, Thinkers Corner, Enugu.

- Nwokocha, P.I. (2005). *Modern Methods Of Teaching Business Courses*. Modern Printers and Publishers Emene, Enugu.
- Njoku, C. U (2006). Business Education and Value Orientation for National Economic Empowerment and Development. Paper presented at the Owo 2006 Annual Conference of the Association of Business Education of Nigeria (ABEN).
- Obasi, L.O. (1983) *Research Methodology in Social Method in Business and Management Services*. Enugu-Nigeria. Iyke Ventures Productions.
- Okafor, F.N. (1997). *Foundation in Modern Business Book keeping and Accounts*. Fagap Publishers.
- Okeke, T.C, Olisa, M.O. and Eze, G.A (2008) *Research Methods in Business and Management Services*. Enugu-Nigeria. Iyke Ventures Productions.
- Olatoke, M. O. (2004). Methods of Teaching Accounting Courses at Secondary school. *A Course Text on Special Methodology, Generic Science and Calculations for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning of Technical, Vocational and Business Subjects*.
- Onovo, I.J. (2011) Office Practices I. unpublished lecture Note, OSISATECH College Of Education, Enugu.
- Osuala, E.C. (2004). *Principles and Methods of Business and Computer Education*, Enugu. Enugu State. Cheston Agency Ltd.
- Owolabi, J.A. and Jegede, P.O (2005). Vocational Education In Nigeria Secondary School: Gaps Between Policy And Practices. *A Modern School Education Technology Journal*. 8(1), 51.
- Oxford Advanced Learners' Dictionary, 4th Edition, Oxford University, Press.
- Parkhill, L.J. (2011). What is Business Studies? www.eduresource.com
- Paul E. O.(2005). *Modern Methods of teaching Business Courses*. Modern Printers and publishers Emene, Enugu.
- Popham, E.L., Schrag, A.F., and Blocklvs (1971). *A Teaching learning System for Business Education*. New York: Megraus.
- Post-Primary School Management Board Statistical Unit of Enugu Educational Zone (PPSMB).
- Rev. Fr. Denis A. (2010). *The Rise and fall of Educational Studies in Nigeria: Implications and Way Forward*. El'Demak Publishers, Enugu.
- Ref. Fr. Eugene U.I.(2010). *The Rise and fall of Education Today*. Lay Apostolate Publishers, Enugu.
- Sir Isaac, P. (2001). *New Course on Pitman Shorthand*. Pitman Publishing.
- Facilities Planning and Management (www.fpm.iastate.edu/worldclass/cgi.asp)
- Wikipedia - <http://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/kaizen> (2014)